

Appendix D – First Version of the MPO

MODEL FOR PROJECTS OBSERVATORIES (MPO)

1. INTRODUCTION

Observation has always been a fundamental element of management and, indeed, of everyday life. This observation, applied to the context of management, according to Bernstein (2017), originates from the observation of natural phenomena and the creation of the scientific method. Furthermore, according to the same author, transparency has emerged as the most recent construct in the attempt to define observation in management. This transparency, according to Betta and Boronina (2018), is a necessary condition and tool for project management.

Nunes, Cappelli, and Ralha (2017) state that the development of mechanisms to systematize transparency has presented a challenge for organizations. In this sense, observatories present themselves as information systems that can provide transparency by supporting the collection, organization, storage, analysis, and publication of observations (HORSBURGH et al., 2010). There is no consensus definition in the literature for the concept of "observatories"; however, Vieira et al. (2020), after analyzing a considerable number of published works, suggested the following definition for observatories: an instrument, mechanism, process, or organizational unit that enables the observation of something, providing transparency through the collection, consolidation, storage, study, research, analysis, sharing, monitoring, and dissemination of data, information, and knowledge from (and for) a specific community. Table 1 presents examples of observatories with web pages available online.

Table 1 - Examples of Observatories

Observatory	Web Page
Observatório do Plano Nacional da Educação	https://observatoriodopne.org.br/
Observatório Nacional de Segurança Viária	https://www.onsv.org.br/
Observatório Social do Brasil	https://osbrasil.org.br/
Observatório da Covid-19	https://www.ufpe.br/observatorio-covid-19
Web Observatory	https://www.webscience.org/web-observatory/
Urban Observatory	https://www.urbanobservatory.org/

Based on the definition presented in Vieira et al. (2020), we understand project observatories as instruments or mechanisms of transparency, based on a computational system, that allow a community to: observe, analyze, and reflect on projects; collect and produce large amounts of data on projects; discuss and present reflections on projects; monitor projects; gather and manage various information about projects; and share knowledge about projects. It is important to emphasize that the results obtained from the development and use of project observatories can be used to support project management; however, these observatories should not replace project management systems (e.g., Microsoft Project, Jira, Trello). The characteristics underlying project observatories are complementary to those existing in project management systems. Table 2 presents examples of observatories available online.

Table 2 - Examples of Project Observatories

Project Observatory	Web Page
Observatório Universal de Projetos	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EnCXLZJhIRE&t=7s
Observatórios de Projetos dos Institutos Federais do Norte	https://sites.google.com/view/opalaif/p%C3%A1gina-inicial?authuser=0
Observatório ObrasPE	http://34.73.156.239/

The Model for Projects Observatories (MPO) was conceived to support the understanding and development of project observatories and was developed from the execution of a set of exploratory studies aimed at executing pilot projects for project observatories. Additionally, a systematic mapping of the literature on observatories was also used as a source for the construction of the model.

The MPO represents an ideal or conceptual vision and not a normative definition. In this sense, it is not expected/required that a project observatory express all aspects of the model. Indeed, it is expected that these aspects will develop/adapt over time. There is also no concern on the part of the MPO to present a sequence for the implementation of its dimensions and elements; thus, the process of developing project observatories based on the MPO is flexible and adaptable to the context of the observatory. More details about the MPO are presented in the following sections.

2. MODEL ORGANIZATION

The MPO was structured into three dimensions: Structures, Processes, and Agents. These dimensions were defined based on the analysis of observatory models presented in Yoshiura et al. (2018) and Brown (2017). The dimensions group a set of subdimensions which, in turn, gather a set of elements. Figure 1 illustrates the dimensions and subdimensions that make up the model.

Figure 1 – Model for Projects Observatories (MPO)

- Structures Dimension: This dimension presents a structural and static view of project observatories. In this dimension, elements related to the subdimensions of components, contents, and characteristics of project observatories are grouped.
- Processes Dimension: This dimension encompasses the processes that can be executed in (and by) project observatories, presenting the observatories from a dynamic perspective. These processes are grouped into the subdimensions of Data Input and Output and Data Processing.

- **Agents Dimension:** This dimension considers the actors involved with project observatories and their respective motivations. In this dimension, elements related to the subdimensions of actors and motivations are grouped.

3. STRUCTURES DIMENSION

The elements of the Structures dimension are grouped into the subdimensions: Components, Contents, and Characteristics. This dimension presents project observatories from a structural perspective. Figure 2 visually presents the subdimensions and the elements grouped within this dimension.

Figure 2 - Structures Dimension

The Components subdimension groups the following structural elements that make up project observatories:

- **Input:** pertains to components related to the collection of project-related data.
- **Storage:** relates to the existence of a repository for storing collected project data.
- **Coordination:** involves structures that coordinate relationships between actors and their interaction with projects and the observatory.
- **Processing:** relates to the processing of collected project data.
- **Output:** relates to the dissemination and sharing of results obtained from data collection and processing.

The Contents subdimension, related to the Structures dimension, deals with the possible themes and content found in project observatories. This subdimension can be understood through the following elements:

- **Projects:** Observatories may contain data related to projects including scope, schedule, costs, quality, resources, communication, risks, acquisitions, and stakeholders.
- **Theme:** Observatories may feature content related to their theme, such as news, events, and developed studies.

- Observations: Observatories may include observations made by human actors on other contents of the observatory. These observations can be presented in the form of comments and reactions.

The Characteristics subdimension, related to the Structure dimension of the model, encompasses both the characteristics of observatories and the characteristics of the data contained within these observatories. This subdimension groups elements related to: access, completeness, delimitation, data format, and interaction.

- Access: Observatories can be characterized as open or semi-open. In open observatories, all information contained within them is publicly accessible, whereas semi-open observatories contain both public and private information.
- Completeness: The presence of incomplete or private information in projects requires project observatories to be capable of storing partial data about these projects.
- Delimitation: Project observatories need to have their scope clearly defined. This scope may relate to themes, geographic region, or the organization (or set of organizations) executing the projects contained within the observatories.
- Data Format: Data stored in project observatories can be structured, meaning organized in a structured format (e.g., project attributes), or unstructured, where data does not have a defined structure (e.g., photos and videos).
- Interaction: Users' interaction with observatories may involve data entry for projects, making observations on projects, constructing analyses, or simply viewing information contained within the observatories.

4. PROCESSES DIMENSION

The Processes dimension encompasses the processes that can be executed in (and by) project observatories. These processes are grouped into the subdimensions: Data Input and Output, and Data Processing. This dimension presents these observatories from a dynamic perspective. Figure 3 visually presents this dimension.

Figure 3 - Processes Dimension

The Data Input and Output subdimension, related to the Processes dimension, groups elements related to:

- **Collection:** Data and information about projects are identified and gathered. This collection can be done manually or automatically.
- **Storage:** The collected data and information about projects are stored in a specific repository.
- **Sharing:** Data and information (raw or processed results) from projects are disclosed/shared with a particular audience.

The Data Processing subdimension, related to the Processes dimension, groups elements related to:

- **Analysis:** Build analyses based on collected data and information about projects.
- **Debate:** Conduct debates based on collected data and information about projects.
- **Reflection:** Develop critical reflections on projects.
- **Evaluation:** Collaboratively evaluate projects and the collected information about them.
- **Integration:** Integrate different data sources and patterns related to projects.
- **Categorization:** Categorize and relate projects.
- **Visualization:** Create visualizations of project data.
- **Prioritization:** Prioritize projects within a portfolio.
- **Prediction:** Predict schedule delays and cost overruns in projects.
- **Validation:** Validate project data and information.
- **Coordination:** Coordinate relationships between actors and between them and the observatory.
- **Collaboration:** Collaborate on projects.
- **Monitoring:** Monitor projects and their progress.
- **Observation/Comment:** Make observations and comments on projects.
- **Reporting:** Report false projects and information.
- **Interaction:** Interact with actors and projects.

5. AGENTS DIMENSION

The Agents dimension encompasses the actors involved with project observatories and their respective motivations. Thus, this dimension consists of the subdimensions Actors and Motivations. Figure 4 visually details the content of this dimension.

Figure 4 - Agents Dimension

The Actors subdimension, related to the Agents dimension, aims to map the actors who can interact with project observatories. In this sense, the elements of this subdimension consist of actors:

- Humans: Stakeholders (individuals and organizations that affect or can be affected by the projects) represent the human actors of project observatories.
- Systems: Non-human actors, referred to here as systems, are represented by project management systems and open databases, which observatories may communicate with to consume data about projects.

The Motivations subdimension, related to the Agents dimension, deals with the motivations that can drive actors to interact with project observatories. The following elements related to this subdimension have been identified:

- Knowledge: Acquisition and construction of new knowledge.
- Learning: Learning through collaboration and knowledge sharing about projects.
- Innovation: Promoting innovation in projects and the products and services they produce.
- Improvement: Seeking improvement in projects and their management.
- Decision Making: Supporting decision-making in projects.
- Control: Control over project planning and execution.
- Visibility: Publicity and visibility of projects.
- Interaction: Facilitating interaction among project stakeholders.
- Transparency: Providing transparency to projects.
- Multiplication: Multiplying positive experiences in projects.
- Participation: Encouraging more active participation of various stakeholders in project planning and execution.

6. REFERENCES

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